

The Expanding Universe Delusion Caused by the Doppler Effect in the Human Brain

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Abstract

Isaac Newton (1643-1727) introduced physics mechanics that yielded successful results for an Earth-sized environment. In the following years, it is observed that these successful mechanics led to wrong results in wider regions. Albert Einstein (1879-1955) accepted the speed of light as a constant to correct these errors and introduced the idea of "special relativity" in this context. This idea does not adequately explain the "visible universe" formed as a web of galaxies and its microwave history. The fact that the cosmic microwave background radiation is in the form of a geoid rather than a sphere proves that the speed of light varies slightly between universal dimensions. In connection with this, the Doppler effect creates a critical delusion in the human brain. According to this effect, that is considered one of the most vital proofs of the Big Bang theory the universe is expanding. The main problem with this proof is that the center point of the big bang is always at the location of the observer. The fact is that explosion that occurs in a single region cannot have countless different explosion centers. That leads to the conclusion that the expanding universe model is a brain delusion.

Key Words: speed of light, cosmic microwave background radiation, doppler effect, big bang

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Introduction

Cosmic microwave background radiation was discovered in 1964 by American astronomers Arno Allan Penzias and Robert Woodrow Wilson. Cosmic microwave background radiation is electromagnetic radiation thought to come from Big Bang Theory. This glow is considered by numerous physicists to be the strongest proof of the Big Bang theory. The findings obtained from measurements enabled the creation of a 3-dimensional (3D) map of the electromagnetic radiation of the observed universe. Doppler Effect is used to explain this mapping. According to the Doppler effect, wavelengths of distant galaxies and light moving away from a constant point are redshifted. As a result of this 3D mapping, galaxies are farther from Earth are

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thought to be moving away from each other faster than nearby galaxies.

Figure 1. Cosmic Microwave Background (Source: The European Space Agency Official Website)

Variability of the Speed of Light

Another detail has been figured out thanks to the findings obtained over years on the cosmic microwave background radiation. This detail, which has not been explained much, is that the 3D map of the cosmic microwave background radiation is not spherical as expected. If the speed of light and its structural types, such as microwaves, are constant, then the distance between the point and the farthest points of the universe will be constant. As a result, we would see the universe as sphere-shaping since the light comes from the farthest points of the universe at the same speed. Although the case is supposed, the result is different. The 3D map of the observed and its microwave background radiation are in geoid form. The result is due to the speed of light and microwaves moving from points at the edge of the visible universe varying.

The variability of the speed of light is not high enough to be noticed when measured for an environment the size of earth and star systems. When the measurement is for the huge galaxy network, the difference in the speed of light can be observed. The speed of light is faster in the wider equatorial plane of the geoid structure (middle of the shape) while the light is slower in the polar plane (up and down ends of the shape) or is perceived as it can be seen in Figure 1. The reason why the speed of light is slower in the polar plane and faster in the equatorial plane is that the density fields in the universe and the

gravity associated affect the speed of light. In addition, dark matter, dark energy, and things that have not been discovered yet may be the cause. Speed of light in space is under no influence and cannot be determined precisely, as there is no "absolute nothingness" utterly free of the effects just mentioned or has yet to be discovered. The accurate speed of light may not be known until a medium that satisfies the conditions is found.

A Thought Experiment on the Variability of the Speed of Light

Suppose the observer is in the middle of a circle on flat terrain with no visible ends. Let's imagine light sources at the end of this circle. The lights come out at the same speed and in the same direction toward the observer. Each path of the lights has different densities and effects from each other. These lights will reach the observer at different times due to the difference in the pathlines. If the observer is unaware of the effect of different environments that lights pass and thinks that each of the lights reaching her at the same speed, the terrain map the observer will draw based on these lights will be wrong. Because the speed of light is constant (v) and so, acceleration is zero, length (x) can be calculated for constant time interval will be wrong due to $x=v*t$ formula. Although the speeds of each light are different, they vary according to the environment and the plane because speed changes concerning the environment effect. All ambient influences should be considered to find the accurate speed of the lights in a particular field. If not so, the observer cannot know the exact speed of light, and so the "real visible area" of the land. The observer cannot see the parts of the field that do not reflect light. In addition, if all of these light sources send light to the observer while they are in motion, the observer will not be able to benefit from the Doppler effect. Because the uncertainty in the speed of light would make it impossible to know which light source was further away and in which direction they were traveling in a 3D coordinate system. Therefore, the data obtained would be a misconception.

Delusion Caused by the Doppler Effect in the Human Brain

The Doppler effect was put forward as a hypothesis in 1842 by the famous scientist Christian Andreas Doppler (1803-1853). It was tried and proven on sound waves by the physicist Christophorus Ballot (1817-1890) in 1845. The effect was applied to electromagnetic waves by the physicist Hippolyte Fizeau (1819-1896) in 1848, and the same result was obtained. Doppler effect is briefly the phenomenon of lengthening the wavelengths of sound and electromagnetic waves emitted by an object approaching the observer and shortening those that move away. When the cosmic microwave background radiation was discovered, the results of this effect on a substance in space were observed, and the way a substance movement was aimed to determine.

Obtained findings show that objects far from the observer have a redder (longer) wavelength than those close. Based on the experiment results, a nearby object is supposed to move away at a slower rate, while objects that are far away from each other at higher acceleration. According to this idea, it ended up the idea that all these objects "explode" away from a single point. This finding has been considered solid proof of the big bang. The key point that is overlooked in the assumption is that if this idea is correct, the center of the big bang must be the Earth. The center point of the Big bang is measured as Earth, or rather the location of the observation. It shows that Earth is the base observation point and assumed as a constant point. However, cosmic microwave background radiation has been observed continuously since 1964, and the Earth does not stand and keeps moving constantly. Therefore, in each observation, the center of the big bang is changing. Undoubtedly, this is a misconception. Accordingly, if it is observed on the moon, we will measure the center of the big bang as the moon. If we had gone further and reached an extreme point in the universe and made this observation there, we would have measured the center of the big bang at that point. For the same reason, the region where the wavelength shifts redder would be at Earth. The reason for that giant error is due to the usage of the Doppler effect in such a case.

Figure 2. Measuring Distance & Move with Redshift (Source: NASA Scientific Visualization Studio)

A Thought Experiment on the Doppler Effect

Consider four cities lined up on a wide, flat plain. Let there be an airport in the first and fourth cities. There is a kid in the second and third cities. An airplane takes off from the first city and travels towards the fourth city at the speed of sound. Both children hear the sound of the plane. As the plane gets closer and closer to the children, the sound they hear is high-frequency. In addition, the frequency increases with the distance decrement through them. Immediately after the plane passes over the second city, the sound frequency heard by the second-city child will momentarily switch to a low frequency as the increment of the distance concerning the child. When they are in the middle of the cities, the child in the second city will hear the low-frequency sound, and the child in the third city will get the high-frequency sound. According to the Doppler effect, the conclusion to be drawn is that the plane moves away from the second city and approaches the third city. Note there are two constant points in this experiment that are second and third cities children. Moving on, let the plane pass over the third city. In this case, both children hear low-frequency waves because the plane is pulling away from both children. However, there is a significant error of thought in this view. The frequency of the wave heard by the second-city child is not the same size as the wave heard by the third-city child. Still, the plane is moving away from both children at the same speed. For that reason, if the velocity is measured by using the Doppler idea at second and third city children, the results will be different from each other and be incorrect, just as scientists measure the wavelengths of galaxies and try to prove the big bang with the Doppler effect.

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